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PREMIER IoT SOLUTION DEVELOPMENT COMPANY –A CASE OF MOBILOITTE

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Abstract

The life is made easy by a rising technology, the Internet of Things, which promised transformation in the way we work, we live, we play, we analyze and we think. The influence of IoT is seen everywhere today, from consumer products to military equipment, from motorbikes to airplanes, from manufacturing units to industries, and from daily use items to utility components and from house to smart cities. The everyday use objects which are being combined with Internet connection and data analytics capabilities guarantee ease of doing work, ease of living, ease of analyzing, ease of thinking and ease of playing. In essence, IoT provides a flat-form to interconnect various electronic devices through the Internet and open up a new world of possibilities. Mobiloitte is a leading complete service solution development company for IoT, AI, and BOTS along other related areas with time, security, scale and performance as its focus points. The company strives for ‘Top Notch Quality Work’ and ‘Complete Customer Satisfaction’ as its business ethics. E3 – Experience, Excellence, and Exuberance is the company’s work motto for the ‘Go-to-Market Strategy’ of the company to provide unique services and solutions to its customers and by that keeping itself in advantage position in the field competition. The company is equally comfortable to work with different types of setups like Start-Ups, Small & Medium Enterprises, Large Enterprises, Development Sector, Public-Private Partnerships, and Governments. Completion of more than 5000 projects in a span of a decade is a testimony to that. In this paper, we made an attempt to analyze various IoT solutions the company provides, highlight their technical backgrounds and list out their applications. At present, the company is providing IoT solutions in large spectrum covering areas like surveillance, power, video inspection, customer feedback, marketing, skill-building, security, etc. In addition, this article also deliberates business challenges and potential solutions to provide different IoT based solutions appropriate to customer requirements and lists out emerging IoT technologies with a futuristic outline.

Keywords: Mobiloitte, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence, 3E, Internet, Solutions.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the world of information technology, the buzzword Internet of Things (IoT) is not recent. It's been in use for a while now. Off late, due to technological advances in wireless technology, the word is attracting more attention and attraction. IoT will expand the scope of the Internet from a mere link provider to various computers and computer equipment to allow

the interconnection of different things, physical objects, we see around us and we are around such things as lamps, fans, air conditioners, toothbrush, microwave oven, pens, televisions, washing machines and so on in our residence, internet-working of different machines or equipments in business, and so on[1]. The IoT technology empowers these ' things ' by talking to each other, sharing information, and synchronizing activities to see, hear, think, speak and perform jobs assigned to them. The very technology allowed them to turn themselves from passive to active and intelligent by supplying the technologies they needed, such as ubiquitous and omnipresent computing, embedded devices, communication systems, sensor networks, protocols and variety of applications. Original IoT was strongly based on Radio Frequency Identification for Interconnection; today there are a number of technologies similar to Radio Frequency Identification, Near Field Communication, Machine-to-Machine and Vehicle-to-Vehicle Communication all may be made use off to implement modern IoT solutions. The IoT technology promised revolution in the way we work, we live, we play, we analyze and we think makes life easy. IoT's influence is seen everywhere today, from consumer products to military equipment, from motorcycles to aircraft, from manufacturing units to industries, from everyday use items to utility components and from home to smart cities[2]. The everyday use objects which are being combined with Internet connection and data analytics capabilities guarantee ease of doing work, ease of living, ease of analyzing, ease of thinking and ease of playing. In essence, IoT provides a flat-form to interconnect various electronic devices through the Internet and open up a new world of possibilities. It was anticipated that every different things we see around us and we have around us will all be internet-worked or interconnected very soon.

IoT Technology primarily benefits industry, governments and consumers. Through their solutions and solutions, each group of its shareholders enjoys different types of benefits.

Reducing operating costs, increasing efficiency, streamlining markets, delivering smart products / services, monitoring customer behavior, etc. are some of the benefits that IoT brings to business. Expanding efficiency, lowering the cost of governance, providing the citizens with sophisticated living environments, securing information, accessibility of people, etc. are the list of benefits that IoT offers to governments. Consumers enjoy enhanced comfort, increased efficiency & experience, added safety & security, decision-making support, and remote control of objects [3].

In this paper, we made an attempt to analyze various IoT solutions Mobiloitte provides, highlight their technical backgrounds and list out their applications. At present, the company is providing IoT solutions in large spectrum covering areas like surveillance, power, video inspection, customer feedback, marketing, skill-building, security, etc. In addition, this article also deliberates business challenges and possible solutions to provide different IoT based solutions appropriate to customer requirements and lists out emerging IoT technologies with a futuristic outline.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To provide overview of IoT Technology
- To understand IoT Application Development
- To know IoT solution development for end-users
- To familiarize IoT solutions development for Industry
- To comprehend enabling technologies for IoT
- To analyze future scope

3. BACKGROUND

Mobilotte is a leading complete service solution development company for IoT, AI, BOTS along other related areas with time, security, scale and performance as its focus points. The company strives for 'Top Notch Quality Work' and 'Complete Customer Satisfaction' as its business ethics. E3 – Experience, Excellence, and Exuberance is the company's work motto for the 'Go-to-Market Strategy' of the company to provide unique services and solutions to its customers and by that keeping itself in advantage position in the field competition. The company is equally comfortable to work with different types of setups like Start-Ups, Small & Medium Enterprises, Large Enterprises, Development Sector, Public-Private Partnerships, and Governments. Completion of more than 5000 projects in a span of a decade is a testimony to that. Headquartered at New Delhi, the company has development centers at Bengaluru and Gurugram and Client Proximity Centers at Singapore, USA, UK, Canada and Norway [4].

4. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

How will it happen? The different things, the seats, the tables, the lighting systems, the watches, or whatever, all we can really think of, will be equipped with embedded systems. These embedded systems, together with embedded electronics, embedded processors, embedded communication systems, allow some basic computing platform to be attached to them and they will act as different nodes of that particular Internet, the internet of things. These devices are fitted with embedded systems that help them link different things around them and depending on the application requirements, depending on the specific objectives of the business and then a huge network will be created that is much larger than the current computer internet and that is the internet-work, internet of things, IoT[5][6].

According to Mario Morales, IDC, by 2020, IoT will have 4 billion connected people, \$4 trillion in revenue generation, over 25 million Applications, over 25 billion embedded and smart devices, and about 50 trillion Bigabits of Information. These figures show how quickly technology is growing [7].

5. IoT SOLUTIONS FOR END-USERS

Surveillance System: Home Security became one of the need-of-the-time things in today's global village perspective world. Requirement of a technology that allows keeping an eye on the aged people, kids or pets at home remotely is felt by many. A low cost and handy solution that allows one to view surveillance videos from anywhere in the world with the help of mobile data or wi-fi connection, display alert or firing alarm as per the set rules, and store not viewed videos in a cloud storage for future view are their expectations[8]. Through Surveillance System Solution one can integrate number of IP camera and stream their data into a mobile app using different streaming protocols and compressions methods. This solution guarantees that the user will achieve peace of mind out of this.

Smart Plug & Bulb : Every Home Automation system begins with a Smart Plug. This Internet enabled device can be used to control any electronic or electrical units of the home. By configuring the device to home wi-fi one can control it through mobile app. The added feature of the device is that, it is also used to monitor energy parameters, power consumptions, line voltages and power factors. This class of solution helps to design and develop such devices and integrate them with the mobile app. This will help the user to

operate home appliances such as ACs, Refrigerators, TVs, Microwave Ovens, Fans, Lights, etc, monitor energy trends and power factors remotely.

Customer Feedback : In the success of any business the continuous feedback from the end-user plays a major role. Collecting feedback instantly, i.e. immediately after the service is provided or product delivery is more realistic and precise rather than doing so after a long gap. From this, the company can improve its service and products. Just in-time feedback is more critical to service business compare to product business. Service business like hotels, restaurants, hospitals, home-stays, clinic, saloons, spa, etc., rely much on customer satisfaction. The company has a tested IoT based solution for this. The low-cost touch enabled device and associated services customized for the business specific requirements can be bought by the business provider on monthly basis to collect on-spot, just-in-time, instant feedback. The device is compatible to connect to 3G/4G networks or wi-fi. Summary of feedback can be viewed either on mobile or on the web portal. Moreover, one can avail additionally clubbed services like weekly report, email notification, inventory management, and consolidated data for chain stores from it.

Video Inspection: Industry 4.0 or connected factory or smart factory is well being adopted by manufacturing units to enhance production. It is adding a special value to the industry by integrating operation technology with information technology and by that gain competitive advantage. Manufacturing units now focused to track the use of their products by the end customer directly and analyze the records to improve quality for products to be produced or being produced. To serve the purpose, the complete value chain strategy from suppliers to end-customer to be connected. – supplier->manufacturer->logistics->warehouse->retailer->customer. Best quality of images or videos of products captured from different stages of production is fed into the ‘learning service’, that in turn develop an analytical model to discern ‘OK vs NOT OK’ features of units that either met with quality specification or not[9].

Real-Time Asset Management (RTAM): Whether it is retail, manufacturing, distribution or shipping for any type of business, the planning and management of inbound raw materials and outbound finished goods is a challenge to monitor through conventional supply chain systems. Materials are often inappropriately trafficked or deposited, which in turn impacts items. Use of Real-Time Location Systems (RTLS) addresses this issue and improves supply chain management logistics. The solution is given by using two prevalent Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technology iBeacon and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID). With Beacon Tags and Beacon Gateways, Mobiloitte offers this solution class. Nevertheless, consumers are equipped with a Mobile and Web Interface that allows easy monitoring of resources. For connectivity, the company uses WiFi or 3G/4G network. It provides various classes of RTAM solutions based on customer infrastructure, expected level of accuracy, a security requirement, and intended type of ownership [10].

BP Marketing: Beacon is a lightweight, tiny radio transmitter based on Bluetooth. Beacon-enabled system transmits a signal that can be seen when any Bluetooth embedded device such as smartphones appears in the scope. The technology empowers retail sellers to research, grasp and evaluates customer buying trends. In this perspective, by integrating online and in-store shopping information, customer loyalty solutions by allowing smartphone-based loyalty programs, Mobiloitte focuses on enhanced customer shopping experience, customized deals based on personal buying patterns and navigation for customers to help monitor retailers[11].

Asset Management & Tracking : Real Time Location System (RTLS) helps the supply chain management system to schedule and control the movement of raw materials and

finished goods. This will reduce waste and improve logistics. All this is possible with the use of two core technologies, iBeacon allowed by Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags. The company uses Beacon Tags and Beacon Gateway to manage Real Time Asset Management. Such customers can use mobile apps and web portals to track property.

Smart Office: A smart office environment creates an atmosphere for employees to work better, easier, more effectively and diligently. By using different sensors and tailored software, an office can be made intelligent so that the human resources available can be used for increasing business and marketing capabilities management. Smart Office Environment can boost productivity, reduce maintenance costs, streamline business operations and save resources. Mobilotte has a solution that can be personalized by ensuring efficient office management and increased productivity to the working environment of any form of workplace.

Door Lock and Camera System: Security is becoming one of the prime components of any kind of setup, whether it is for families, homes, individual shops, offices, businesses or departments. Using a smart lock, doors can be opened or closed remotely via a mobile app or at the doorstep, as well as video streaming of the activities at the doorstep. Mobilotte has built-in firmware and app smart lock solution that uses home wifi connectivity.

Lighting System: Smart lighting system includes features that collect energy-related data such as power consumption, power factor and voltage. The application or web portal allows users to view trend data that can be used for decision making. Mobilotte helps develop these solutions using smart lights and interfaces preferred by customers. Through this application, one can switch on or off lights, track interval energy consumption, set lighting rules, change the color and intensity of lights, etc., all remotely using either a mobile app or a web portal.

Security Alarm: Home, office and company set-up safety and protection is a concern for its owners. A solution integrated with a fire or smoke detector, a toxic fume sensor, a PIR motion sensor, etc. controlled by microcontroller, will raise and alert the user to situations such as fire by sending an alert message to the mobile device or triggering an embedded buzzer.

Smart Shower: Bluetooth enabled shower head, which can be conveniently controlled with a mobile app, makes showering much easier and more enjoyable. This allows users to steam their favorite music, listen to news or radio, and help minimize water use. Mobilotte has a solution that allows the shower head to pair a portable speaker wirelessly with devices to deliver high-quality audio at the time of the shower.

Kitchen Care: Mobilotte has a flexible kitchen care system that combines Bluetooth or Wi-Fi enabled appliances with mobile apps for tracking and managing them. One can also use the device to order food, monitor the trash bin, read the barcode data attached to the packaged item and manage the inventory of the kitchen.

Garage Control: A microprocessor-controlled smart device can be used to test if garage doors are open or closed, as well as to control the motor to remotely close or open the door whenever appropriate. The company helps its customers build firmware system and mobile app so that users can remotely monitor garage doors and receive correct warning messages[12].

Temperature Control: Many situations require indoor temperature control. It is critical because it offers thermal comfort and a reasonable quality of air. Using smart sensors, temperature control unit demonstrates the ability to monitor heating conditions and manage

heating and cooling systems accordingly. There are also options for creating multiple temperature schedules and managing multiple thermostats.

Voice Service Integration : Mobiloite uses Amazon Alexa as a tool to integrate voice-controlled devices. The company is working in developing voice applications, Chatbots and SMS bots.

IFTT Integration : IFTTT (If This Then That) will make apps and devices work in tandem. With this, a simple script can be created so that an action can quickly cause the same action in another device or app. The company is helping to develop and implement the best efficient IFTTT applications that combine apps and devices.

Smart Garden : With a smart sprinkler, watering can be coordinated from anywhere via the mobile app. The smart garden center is capable of detecting tube leaks and breaks and collaborating with apps for home automation. It uses garden sensors only when necessary to measure weather forecast and water. It also sends alerts and notes on water saving. Watering can be scheduled through the phone [13].

5. IoT SOLUTIONS FOR INDUSTRIES

Mobiloite is also developing a variety of business solutions. The company provides a package of solutions for the telecommunications industry, including energy management, gas, access, alarm, employees, generator, asset tracking, preventive maintenance, monitoring setting, etc[14]. The smart manufacturing approach solves many problems such as production control, resource digitization, capacity utilization, system uptime and downtime tracking, employee management, etc. Education solution tackles problems such as high fees, low student-teacher ratio, sufficient educational material, ward safety and security, learning focused on students and community-based, etc[15]. The solutions include adaptation to new technology, multimedia-based learning, enhanced reality-based education, speech-text translation, student tracking, learning content digitization, etc.. Smart Hospitality solution involves numerous issues such as predictive analysis, helpdesk focused on BOTS, power tracking, football analysis, etc. Smart construction approach combines problems such as smart customer interface, proximity-based advertising, automation, maintenance and management of resources, smart payments, waste management, security systems, etc[16][17].

6. PORTFOLIO

Smaartly - Track the location of the car anytime, check and tag trips, reminder for fuel and oil addition, avoid bad, expensive surprises. Connected Car is a smart plug-and-play app that connects user's car to the Internet to deliver real-time location, travel history, maintenance alerts, engine diagnostics and driving insights to user's smartphone instantly.

LOC84 - Is an OBD scanner link app designed to help simplify your auto life with venue, diagnostics, data driving, warnings, boundaries and more.

Swoope - It's a clever way to get local bars, restaurants, and takeaways to order and pay. Connect mobile wallet directly back to the counter, order for collection, skip the queues in busy bars or start a tab with friends at the end of the night and easily split the bill.

Zipato - enables remote control of light, safety system, heating, cooling, shading or irrigation, track energy consumption and save power. And helps protect your home against theft, explosion, flooding, etc[18].

8. CONCLUSION

The life is made easy by the IoT, which promised transformation in the way we work, we live, we play, we analyze and we think. The influence of IoT is seen everywhere today, from consumer products to military equipment, from motorbikes to airplanes, from manufacturing units to industries, and from daily use items to utility components and from house to smart cities. The everyday use objects which are being combined with Internet connection and data analytics capabilities guarantee ease of doing work, ease of living, ease of analyzing, ease of thinking and ease of playing. In essence, IoT provides a flat-form to interconnect various electronic devices through the Internet and open up a new world of possibilities. A few of them have already been explored and there is a great amount of it is waiting in. By linking smart physical objects together and allowing different applications to help smart decision-making, IoT is expected to be one of the main hubs between different technologies in the years to come. Opportunities are in abundance to Explore, Experiment, and Expedite IoT.

REFERNCES

- [1] Shah, S. H., & Yaqoob, I. (2016). A survey: Internet of Things (IOT) technologies, applications and challenges. 2016 4th IEEE International Conference on Smart Energy Grid Engineering, SEGE 2016, i, 381–385. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SEGE.2016.7589556>Murar,
- [2] M., & Brad, S. (2014). Monitoring and controlling of smart equipments using Android compatible devices towards IoT applications and services in manufacturing industry. *Proceedings of 2014 IEEE International Conference on Automation, Quality and Testing, Robotics, AQTR 2014*, (4), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AQTR.2014.6857841>
- [3] Costa, B., Pires, P. F., Delicato, F. C., Li, W., & Zomaya, A. Y. (2016). Design and Analysis of IoT Applications: A Model-Driven Approach. *2016 IEEE Cyber Science and Technology Congress, CyberSciTech 2016, DASC-PICom-DataCom-CyberSciTech 2016*, 392–399. <https://doi.org/10.1109/DASC-PICom-DataCom-CyberSciTec.2016.81>
- [4] About Us, Mobiloitte. Mobiloitte. Retrieved from <https://www.mobiloitte.com/about-us> on 20/11/2019.
- [5] Murthy, A., Han, D., Jiang, D., & Oliveira, T. (2015). Lighting-Enabled Smart City Applications and Ecosystems based on the IoT. *IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things, WF-IoT 2015 - Proceedings*, 757–763. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WF-IoT.2015.7389149>
- [6] Zhamanov, A., Sakhiyeva, Z., Suliyev, R., & Kaldykulova, Z. (2018). IoT smart campus review and implementation of IoT applications into education process of university. *2017 13th International Conference on Electronics, Computer and Computation, ICECCO 2017, 2018-January*, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECCO.2017.8333334>
- [7] Udoh, I. S., & Kotonya, G. (2018). Developing IoT applications: challenges and frameworks. *IET Cyber-Physical Systems: Theory & Applications*, 3(2), 65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-cps.2017.0068>
- [8] Gaur, A., Scotney, B., Parr, G., & McClean, S. (2015). Smart city architecture and its applications based on IoT. *Procedia Computer Science*, 52(1), 1089–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.05.122>
- [9] Valdivieso Caraguay, Á. L., Benito Peral, A., Barona López, L. I., & García Villalba, L. J. (2014). SDN: Evolution and opportunities in the development IoT applications.

International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks, 2014.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/735142>

- [10] Mohammed, F. H., & Esmail, R. (2015). Survey on IoT Services: Classifications and Applications. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 4(1), 2124–2127.
- [11] Kyriazis, D., Varvarigou, T., White, D., Rossi, A., & Cooper, J. (2013). Sustainable smart city IoT applications: Heat and electricity management & Eco-conscious cruise control for public transportation. *2013 IEEE 14th International Symposium on a World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks, WoWMoM 2013*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/WoWMoM.2013.6583500>
- [12] Talavera, J. M., Tobón, L. E., Gómez, J. A., Culman, M. A., Aranda, J. M., Parra, D. T., Garreta, L. E. (2017). Review of IoT applications in agro-industrial and environmental fields. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 142(118), 283–297.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2017.09.015>
- [13] Mobiloitte. IoT App Development Company, IoT Application Development Services. Mobiloitte. Retrieved from <https://www.mobiloitte.com/internet-of-things/> on 20/11/2019.
- [14] Kaur, M. J., & Maheshwari, P. (2016). Building smart cities applications using IoT and cloud-based architectures. *2016 International Conference on Industrial Informatics and Computer Systems, CIICS 2016*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSII.2016.7462433>
- [15] Dattatraya, V. (2012). Available Online through Research Article. *Ijrap.Net*, 4(1), 4060–4066. Retrieved from <http://ijrap.net/vol2/issue2/5.pdf>
- [16] Wang, Q., Zhao, Y., Wang, W., Minoli, D., Sohraby, K., Zhu, H., & Occhiogrosso, B. (2017). Multimedia IoT systems and applications. *GIoTS 2017 - Global Internet of Things Summit, Proceedings*, (2). <https://doi.org/10.1109/GIoTTS.2017.8016221>
- [17] Internet Of Things (IoT) Industries | IoT Applications | Mobiloitte. Retrieved from <https://www.mobiloitte.com/internet-of-things/iot-industries> on 20/11/2019.
- [18] Portfolio, Mobiloitte. Mobiloitte. Retrieved from <https://www.mobiloitte.com/portfolio> on 20/11/2019.